

Game Mechanics for Transformation

Game Mechanics for Transformation is a card-based toolkit for educators and game designers who want to create meaningful learning experiences—especially around ethics, persuasion, sustainability, and personal or social transformation. It offers 41 game mechanisms to spark ideas quickly and playfully, supported by mission prompts based on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals and 16 ethical issues. The toolkit is grounded in research from Johannes Katsarov’s book *Virtuous Play – Promoting Moral Sensitivity with Digital Games* (2023). The game was developed by Johannes Katsarov, Maya Kim and Johanna Willich and published via Leuphana University Lüneburg in 2026 (CC BY-SA).

Quick-start Formats

Three simple ways to use the cards for brainstorming, lesson activities, and game concept pitches.

1. **Random Combinations** (3+ players, competitive): One player is the **Contractor** each round. **Step 1:** The Contractor draws (or chooses) **one Mission card** (ethics or sustainability) and reads it aloud. **Step 2:** Each player/team draws **three random Mechanism cards**. **Step 3:** Give everyone **1–2 minutes** to create an educational game concept that (a) addresses the mission and (b) uses **all three** mechanisms. **Step 4:** Players/teams pitch (e.g., 30–60 seconds each). **Step 5:** The Contractor awards the “contract” to the best pitch. The winner keeps the Mission card as a point. **Tip:** Rotate the Contractor role every round to keep judging fair and to vary the kind of missions selected.

2. **Stacking** (2+ players, collaborative): Build a single game concept together by adding one strong mechanism at a time. **Step 1:** Draw a random Mission card—or agree on a mission you want to explore. **Step 2:** Each player draws **three Mechanism cards** and selects **one** to propose: explain how it would help a game achieve the mission. **Step 3:** As a group, choose which proposed mechanism(s) to keep **on the table**; shuffle the rest back into the mechanism deck. **Step 4:** Start the next round: everyone discards their hand, draws three new Mechanism cards, and proposes one mechanism that **strengthens** or **combines with** the mechanisms already on the table. **Step 5:** Repeat for **3–5 rounds** (or until you have a clear core loop). **Extended version (constraint):** Set a maximum of **4 mechanisms** on the table. When you want to add a new one beyond the limit, you must replace an existing mechanism and briefly explain why the swap improves the design.

3. **Three Questions** (2+ players, competitive): A fast ideation game where your pitch must answer three design questions. **Setup:** Combine and shuffle (a subset of) Mission and Mechanism cards into one draw pile. Each player draws **3 cards** as a starting hand. Reveal the top card to start a face-up **discard pile**. **Goal:** Create the most valid game ideas in **30 minutes** (or before the draw pile runs out). **On your turn:** (1) Draw **one** card—either from the draw pile or the top of the discard pile. (2) If you can, lay down **1 Mission card + 3 Mechanism cards** and pitch a game concept that achieves the mission and answers all three questions: (a) **Role**—what role do players take? (b) **Challenge**—what do players struggle to achieve/overcome? (c) **Feedback**—what feedback do players receive and how does it guide them? (3) The group may challenge your pitch; if they can explain which question is not clearly supported by at least one mechanism, you must revise or take the cards back into your hand. (4) End your turn by discarding **one** card face-up. **After a successful idea:** Draw cards until you have **4 in hand**, then discard one at end of turn as usual. **Scoring:** Each accepted idea counts as 1 point; highest score wins.